

Structured Literature Survey on Avatars for Collaboration in Virtual and Augmented Reality

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ABSTRACT

Avatars are the key to communicate in immersive environments. They are widely used to represent human actors in collaborative tools to increase the ability to socially interact with other people. To understand research directions regarding avatars, in this paper, we present a structured literature survey based on 49 papers that report on avatar-supported collaboration in Virtual and Augmented Reality published in a selection of different conferences and journals. We used the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines to identify the papers used in our analysis. Our goal is to highlight characteristic avatars and their different dimensions. We characterized the avatars by their representation styles (e.g., realistic, stylized), communication channels (e.g., facial expression, voice) and body motion (e.g., hand gestures, head only) used to animate them. Additionally, we identified different application areas (e.g., medical, education) these avatars are used in. We also observed a coupling between the used communication channels, immersive environment and collaboration type.

Keywords: avatars, virtual reality, augmented reality, collaboration, literature survey

Index Terms: Human-centered computing—Human computer interaction (HCI)—Interaction paradigms—Mixed / augmented reality; Human-centered computing—Human computer interaction (HCI)—Interaction paradigms—Virtual reality; General and reference—Document types—Surveys and overviews

1 INTRODUCTION

Avatars, as a way to communicate in immersive environments, have received substantial attention over the last decades [22, 86]. An avatar is a virtual representation of a user in a virtual environment, which maps the user’s interactions and behaviors to collaborate with other user, where the avatars have *the key role of shaping how the virtual social interaction performs in the multi-user scenarios* [44]. Avatars are specifically relevant for remote collaboration, in which users are not co-present in the same place [18, 63, 95, 96].

Nowadays, avatars can be found in many enterprise systems for daily work [29] and for social communication in consumer applications [84, 99]. For instance, the meeting and collaboration platform VIVE Sync [29] uses a stylized form of human representations, which can be customized to create an individual avatar. In engineering, often more abstract representations, such as robots, are used [2, 15]. Only a few of these tools use individually adjustable avatar representation, in contrast to consumer applications such as VR Chat [84], where users can choose to be represented by almost any representation style or form.

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Several existing surveys covered different aspects related to avatar-supported collaboration in immersive environments. Genay et al. [23] review literature covering the embodiment of virtual self-avatars targeting AR systems. They present a body avatarization continuum inspired by the Reality-Virtuality Continuum suggested by Milgram et al. [56] and suggest that sense of embodiment emerges in the same way as it does in other settings. Caserman et al. [10] surveyed 53 papers and suggest that full-body avatars have the potential to improve immersion in VR. There are studies that include consumer applications into their surveys. For instance, Murphy et al. [59] surveyed 200 consumer VR experiences. and found that agency of virtual actions can be established even with the absence of visible self-avatar parts. Hudson et al. [32] examine avatar appearances in training scenarios and conclude that avatar appearances can affect behavior for improving performances.

These papers cover important areas of VR and AR in general that also cover aspects related to avatars. Namely these are embodiment, presence and other cognitive aspects. Our work is inspired by these systematic reviews and will target publications that encompass avatar-supported collaboration in AR/VR, as this has not been systematically reviewed before. In particular, we are interested in the way avatars are used to enhance social interaction and if different type of avatars can be characterized from the literature. The results from the presented papers will pose as a base for theory-based coding of our selected papers.

The literature has discussed different challenges when designing and using avatars [19, 34, 54]. For instance, it is important to understand who the users of the avatars are and which application domain is targeted. These characteristics might substantially affect how users want to be represented in a collaborative scenario [31]. Also different collaboration setups, taking place co-located or remotely, with multiple users, or in different immersive setups (e.g. Augmented or Virtual Reality), can impact the choices and preferences for avatars. Not only the representation itself, but how the representation is used offers interesting and important research questions. To better characterize the design space of avatars, in this paper we contribute a structured literature survey on avatar representations in collaborative immersive environments. We were inspired by works coming from different areas, such as engineering or gaming [32, 35, 46, 70, 75, 92], targeting topics like embodiment and self-disclosure [79] or medical research [90], which also cover the topic of avatars as a secondary subject.

The goal of this paper is to survey literature based on the status quo of avatar representations used for collaborative Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). We aim to answer the question which representations are predominant in the current literature for avatar-supported collaborative VR and AR research. Additionally, we seek to identify how the visual appearance of avatar representations can be characterized based on the identified literature. We identify the most common representation styles, communication channels and body motion used to animate the avatars. Furthermore, we analyzed the different application areas and collaboration types used in combination with the immersive environments.

Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram of paper selection included in our survey with an iterative approach [53].

2 METHODS

In this work, we aim to capture the current state of research for avatars in collaborative immersive environments. In order to do so, we used the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) approach to structure the evaluation of papers identified in the initial search [53]. PRISMA focuses on ways in which authors can ensure a transparent and complete reporting of the type of research [60], which guides the development of systematic reviews and meta-analyses.

2.1 Eligibility Criteria

Publications considered eligible for inclusion involved papers that cover avatar-supported collaborative VR and AR applications. To ensure a proper comparison, we specifically included both AR and VR experiences. These papers correspond to publications between 2006 - 2022. We decided to exclude publication formats (e.g., posters, demos) that unlikely to contain enough details regarding an evaluation due to their brevity. These formats are usually not reviewed as rigorously.

Overall, our inclusion criteria were:

- 1) has one of the following keywords (or synonyms) in the TITLE-ABS-KEY field [55]: *Virtual Reality* or *Augmented Reality* along with *Avatar* and *Collaboration*;
- 2) is not a poster, demo paper or similar type;
- 3) shows at least one figure of an avatar representation and covers one of the following topics (or synonyms) in the abstract: *Collaboration*, *Social Interaction* ;
- 4) is not only theoretical or a technical support (e.g. a literature review, a system setup without considering avatars in CVEs);
- 5) is included in one of the following venues in the last 20 years: ISMAR [33], CHI [11], VRST [85], VR [83], SIGGRAPH [76], TVCG [82], CSCW [14].

2.2 Search Strategy & Selection

The literature was identified through an extensive search in the Scopus database [55], which includes multiple scholarly libraries. The latest search ran on 25th, Aug 2022.

Having those papers identified, eligibility assessment and data abstraction were performed independently in a conventional unblinded

Table 1: Representation Styles.

keyword	example	chart (2006 - 22)	N
realistic		33	
point cloud		3	
stylized		11	
mannequin		10	
hologram		4	

standardized manner by the first and second author of the paper. Each paper was reviewed by both of them to determine its eligibility.

2.3 Data Collection Process

Fig. 1 provides an overview of the data collection process. The search in the database returned a total of 738 unique records after we removed duplicates and only considered publications from the ACM and IEEE databases. We then identified the most prestigious venues and excluded certain publication types, which resulted in 114 records. The title and abstracts of the unique records were analyzed, taking into account the defined screening criteria. From those, 31 records were excluded for not meeting such criteria. This resulted in 83 records eligible for the full-text analysis. From those 83 records, 33 records were excluded based on the previously defined exclusion criteria resulting in a total of 49 records that were included in the qualitative synthesis.

2.4 Coding Scheme

The selected papers for full-text assessment were reviewed on the basis of a theory-based coding scheme. This included the following variables, but was not restricted to them: collaboration (see Table 2), communication (see Table 3), representation types (see Table 1), display medium (see Table 4), the main findings (see Fig. 2), and application areas (see Table 7). Additionally, we collected metadata, such as keywords and research topics (see Table 6). Based on the data obtained, a quantitative analysis was conducted. The quantitative analysis also comprised a set of charts that summarize the selected works in groups, taking into account the research questions of this systematic review.

3 RESULTS

Our results are organized according to a theory-based coding scheme presented in Sec. 2.4. A summary of the resulting papers together with their main findings, representation style, collaboration type and application area is shown in Fig. 2. Additionally, we present our results with meaningful visualizations.

3.1 Avatar Representation

Our main goal for this review was to characterize different types of avatars used in collaborative immersive environments. The rep-

Figure 2: Overview of all publications included in our survey ordered by application area: general purpose (GP), medical (M), training and education (TE), gaming (G), and physical task (PT). Modalities are sorted by their number of occurrences (bottom).

Table 2: Collaboration Types.

keyword	description	chart (2006 - 22)	N
co-located	working together virtually in the same physical space		12
distributed	working together on a subject from different locations		19
remote	working from different locations, collaboration is usually combined with a desktop system or unilateral		19

Table 3: Communication Channels.

keyword	example	chart (2006 - 22)	N
body movement	describes the mere movement of the avatars body (e.g. gestures and postures)		42
eye gaze	a persons captured eye gaze when looking at a virtual object or actor, tracked by eye trackers or simulated		8
facial expression	motions and muscle movement of a users face, tracked (e.g. through voice or cameras) or simulated		4
voice	verbal expressions that is transmitted to the collaboration partner		28

resentation style describes the static visual representation of a user and includes texturization and the 3D representation. We identified five main styles of avatars: point cloud, realistic, stylized and mannequins (see Fig. 2). A summary of the classified main avatar styles can be found in Table 1. We found that most papers use realistic avatars (33 of 49), followed by stylized (11 of 49), mannequin representations (10 of 49), holograms (4 of 49) and point clouds (3 of 49).

In the papers we collected, we found that stylized avatars were more broadly used starting from 2018 (see miniature line chart in Table 1). In contrast, realistic avatars have been used throughout the years, whereas mannequins were used more frequently in collaborative scenarios after 2019. Realistic avatars are characterized by a style that tries to represent the user in the most natural way, with a natural body shape and a natural skin texture. A solution to represent the actor with the aim to create the most realistic appearance is the use of point cloud avatars [1]. Some papers use point clouds to create a digital copy of the actor and create a textured, rigged avatar [37, 96]. This style has, from a visual perspective, the most details and accuracy to a real person [57]. Yu et al. [96] used a live transmitted point cloud to teleport a actor from one location to another by an avatar and compare to a classical realistic avatar. Their solution has technical restrictions, but already reveals a new way of creating presence in the field of social interaction. For static tasks, a point cloud can achieve higher social presence. In contrast, the

Table 4: Immersion Medium.

keyword	example	chart (2006 - 22)	N
virtual reality	fully immersed in a virtual environment, separated from the real world		42
augmented reality	real-world environment enhanced with virtual elements		14

Table 5: Body Representation.

keyword	example	chart (2006 - 22)	N
full-body	full body representation with legs and arms attached to the virtual body		38
hand gestures	only hands are used to visualize the avatar or self-avatar		14
head only	only the head of the user is displayed, no hands are visible		7
inverse kinematic	when inverse kinematic is implemented, the arms of the avatar can move in a more natural way, based on head and hand position		8
upper body with head	same as full-body, without legs and feet		8

		immersion		
		AR	VR	
collaboration	co-located	body movement		2 1 6 7
		eye gaze		1
		facial expression		1 1 1
		voice		2 1 4 2
	distributed	body movement	2 1 1 4 1	2 3 2 8 1
		eye gaze	2 1 1	1 1 1
		facial expression	1 1	1 1
		redirected gaze	1	1
	remote	body movement	2 2 1 8 1	2 2 2 11 2
		eye gaze	2 2 1	2 4 1
		facial expression	1	
		redirected gaze	1 1	1 1
		1 1 1 3	1 2 2 6 2	

hologram point cloud stylized
 mannequin realistic

Figure 3: Observed combinations of modalities collaboration, communication and type of immersion. The color of each dot represents a representation style of the avatar. The size of the dot represents the number of occurrences.

eye contact was rated better for pre-scanned avatars. With regard to perception, point cloud avatars are the most promising solution [97].

We identified two main forms of stylized avatars, textural abstraction and body shape abstraction. The actor can still be identified by a dedicated visual representation with human lookalike, but the texture and shape tend towards artificiality [57, 94]. Abstract avatars are suited for playful private activities [94] or when eye gaze should be very obvious in an collaboration scenario [78]. An even more abstracted form of avatars is the use of mannequins. Here, the actor does not have a dedicated texture or realistic body shape [72, 77, 80].

Three identified publications also investigate the size of an avatar [38, 63, 87]. By adding a miniature version of an avatar constantly in the viewpoint to a normal avatar shows that awareness and social presence can be increased [63]. However, Walker et al. [87] found that equal-sized avatars are more powerful than smaller avatars with regard to the attention focus, showing that further research is needed.

3.2 Immersive Medium

For the immersion type, we differentiate mainly between AR (14 of 49) and VR (42 of 49), as these two were predominant during our evaluation. Table 4 visualizes trends of using immersive tech-

Table 6: Research Topics.

keyword	example	chart (2006 - 22)	N
awareness	refers to a person’s current, situational consciousness or <i>awareness</i> of their surroundings		11
embodiment	cognitive science term, according to which consciousness requires a body, i.e. physical interaction		13
body ownership	perceptual state, refers to the feeling of the body as your own		6
presence	describes a feeling of being engaged in an immersive environment		39
human factors	collective term for mental, cognitive and social influencing factors in systems		23
tracking	describes the technological side of tracking body parts of physical objects		6
trust	refers to having confidence in using an immersive system and interacting with collaborations partners		4
medical information systems	describes systems that use data and information necessary for applying virtual health care		3
teleconsultation	refers to consultations with a customer-vendor-relationship, e.g. patient and doctor, but is not limited to it		4

nologies for avatar-supported collaboration. Using AR, as well as VR peaked in 2019 and significantly dropped in 2020, potentially due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on conference venues and traveling restrictions. The publication data we collected by then shows that publications increased in 2022 again, keeping in mind that some venues might not have released all publications by then. This lead us to the assumption that publications in the field of collaborative immersive environments supported by avatars will follow the prior ascending trend.

When looking at the relation of application domains and hardware, we saw a small tendency that collaborative avatars were more used in AR for medical use cases (2 of 14, 14,3%) than in VR (5 of 42, 12%) (see Fig. 3). In VR, instead, training use cases were used

Table 7: Application Domains.

keyword	example	chart (2006 - 22)	N
general purpose	a broader topic was explored without having a specific domain in mind		34
training & education	teach actors something (e.g. school) or to train them for a specific usage domain		7
medical	medical examinations (e.g. operations) or consultations in the medical field with patients		5
physical task	covers tasks in which the goal is to move physical objects		4
gaming	avatars used in the field of collaborative immersive games and entertainment media (e.g. social media)		2

more often (4 of 42, 9.5%) than in AR (0 of 14, 0%). With regard to the representation, we did not find a clear tendency towards a specific style, as the styles were distributed evenly across all display mediums.

3.3 Collaboration

Remote and distributed collaboration (each 19 of 49) were used most of the time, followed by co-located (12 of 49) collaboration (see Table 2). Meaning that most collaboration did not take place in the same space. The same tendency was identified when looking at the type of immersive environment. Thus, avatar-supported systems are most likely to be used when collaboration is not taking place in the same place and where avatars have the highest potential to enrich the communication between actors. Yet, sometimes the *first life* seems to disrupt the immersive experience [17]. Here, we also found that realistic avatars are particularly used in co-located collaboration (6 of 12 times), when actors seemingly know each other, and embodiment and ownership have a higher relevance [72]. Fribourg et al. [20] also found that collaborating in a virtual environment is more efficient when performing tasks, which was also discovered by other researchers [7]. Holograms and point cloud avatars were used for every collaboration type, mostly for augmented reality (3 of 4). We also found that for AR, distributed (7 of 14) and remote (9 of 14) collaboration is mainly used opposed to co-located collaboration (0 of 14).

3.4 Communication

Communication is an important topic when collaborating in immersive environments, particularly when the collaboration takes place in a distributed or remote setting. We identified five main communication channels (see Table 3). Here, we found that voice (29 of 49) and body movement (45 of 49) is used by most systems as well as avatar representations, probably due to the fact that both channels are the easiest to implement in a prototypical study setup with most consumer HMDs. Non-verbal communication channels, such as eye gaze, facial expressions or emotions are used at least once in every collaboration type across the data we collected. Differences exist in the shaping of the channels, making non-verbal communication an important factor to shape social interaction [72, 73]. Although non-verbal communication seems important in general, voice is not used as often, or it was not mentioned in the papers. We assume that voice as a communication modality was not relevant in the given investigation context, and thus, not mentioned in the paper.

Non-verbal cues are an often discussed topic when talking about avatars for AR and VR applications. The cues are depended on sensor data, which creates a movement of the avatars facial expression or additional visualizations, such as a visualized ray to display further information to ease communication. [62] presented different cues, that can be used within an avatar mediated collaboration: head movement, eye gaze or hand gestures (see Table 5). Piumsomboon et al. [63] use a miniaturized avatar version which is always in the field of view and supports collaboration with hand gestures and a redirected pointing ray, which can *convey the non-verbal communication cues necessary to improve the performance on an asymmetric object placement task*. Yoon et al. [95] and Kim et al. [40] also redirecting cues. Here the pointing gesture of a user is retargeted to the perspective of a user. In contrast, Roth et al. [72] summarize that *the absence of important behavioral cues such as gaze and facial expression can partly be compensated for a ball game and a verbal task*. Thanyadit et al. [80] show, that a ray showing the gaze direction of learners in an immersive learning experience is best for the instructor to observe the learning process. Jing et al. [36] visualize gaze direction in a similar manner.

The richness of information an avatar represents varies in the identified literature. Most of the information investigated by the publications is of visual nature [43, 50, 94], only a few publications

within the context of this survey mention or investigate sound as a support channel for information [6]. The represented visual information can be separated into movement information and static information. Movement information represents the position of different body parts of a user. This includes user position [39], extremities movement [58], finger/pointing movement [95], head movement [62], eye/gaze movement [80], and also facial movement [50]. The amount of movement information varies from one publication to another and sometimes was the study focus itself [77]. The way the movement is tracked varies also [50, 94].

Piumsomboon et al. [62] use multiple non-verbal cues in their presented system for avatar-mediated immersive collaboration for a natural looking avatar, such as head gaze, eye gaze and hand gestures. In later work, Piumsomboon et al. [63] use miniaturized avatars supported by hand gestures and a redirected pointing ray, which can convey the non-verbal communication cues necessary to improve the performance on an asymmetric object placement task. Yoon et al. [95] use retargeted pointing gestures based on the perspective of the actor. Roth et al. [72] even state that the absence of important behavioral cues such as gaze and facial expression can partly be compensated, showing that an avatar does not necessarily need to address every communication channel.

3.5 Body Representation

We also coded the type of body representation (e.g. full-body, hands only) (see Table 5 and Fig. 3). Additional to static visualizations, such as style and body parts, movement visualization is included in the identified literature. To start with the lowest representation richness of movement, all identified publications use head position and rotation as an initial input for the position of an avatar. Piumsomboon et al. [62] apply the position and rotation of an HMD to a static 3D head model to represent a users position and viewing direction. Moustafa et al. [58] and Yoon et al. [94] add kinematic to the upper body to separate the head rotation from the upper body rotation. The position of an user can be enriched with the position and rotation of extremities. Other researchers [62,94] add hand position and rotation to a static hand mesh to represent the users hands in a head and hand set up. For a upper body set up Yoon et al [94] and Wang et al. [88] apply the position of hands to a rigged upper body to visualize arm movement. In case of a full-body avatar, legs and feet movement can also present with additional tracking [25, 94]. Finger movement can be represented by avatars as well. Additional tracking enabled pointing gestures [62] and enables the exact representation of finger movement by sensor gloves [95]. Facial expressions are also used by several researchers. Lugin et al. [50] and Hart et al. [26] track faces to visualize facial expressions on an avatars. Separated from facial expressions, some paper also include eye and gaze visualization onto avatars [62, 78]. The tracking is displayed by eye movement [78] or a ray cast/field of view visualization [36, 62]. Beside movement itself, the realism of movement is highlighted to be important as participants preferred realistic body posture and hand gesture while talking [91]. This is especially important as kinematics can produce strange looking postures or human behaviors.

The amount of modalities for body representation varies throughout the literature. Some papers explicitly put their main emphasis on the body representation itself [43, 94]. Wang et al. [88] present results for the remote instruction use case with significant better system usability scale for a whole body constellation compared to a hand only set up and a higher mean value compared to a hand and arm set up. A full-body avatar seems to be better for following movement of other users and is more easy to understand compared to a hand only constellation. Their results also show better tracking and understanding in contrast to a hand and arm set up. Yoon et al. [94] investigate a similar constellation with a full-body vs. an upper body vs. hand and head set up. They conclude, that a full-body is the better solution regarding social presence. But a full-body avatar in

Figure 4: Matrix visualizing the ethnic and gender of avatars we observed during coding. The size of the dot represents the number of occurrences.

an AR use case is only adding value, when the lower body is in view of the collaborators, which is not always supported by current AR hardware. If people are closer to each other within collaboration, the lower body parts do not add any value. Most of the identified literature use full-body avatars in AR (16 of 20) and VR (26 of 34). Only a few researchers use upper body with head (2 of 20 for AR and 5 of 34 for VR) or head only (5 of 20 for AR and 5 of 34 for VR) constellations for social collaboration [9, 24, 28, 36, 42, 62, 91]. In VR most of the avatars (26 of 34) are full-body. Body ownership, as investigated by Hagiwara et al. [25], seems to be the biggest reasoning. In contrast, in AR users can see their own physical body the whole time. In VR, the physical body has to be replaced by a virtual one. To immerse the user and have a high self embodiment, a full-body avatar seems to be the most beneficial solution.

Tracking and sensors have a direct impact on the information richness of avatar movement representation. Some AR and VR HMDs already include different software and hardware equipment, which result in different capabilities to represent and visualize an avatar. VR HMDs usually come with a HMD and controllers. This set up allows to visualize the avatars head position and rotation as well as hand position and rotation. Upper body and arms need to be estimated by kinematics [94]. Hand gestures in a VR set up can be abstracted by controller input [91]. For instance, when the grab button is pressed, the avatar is performing a grab gesture. To visualize exact finger movement, additional tracking is needed [62] in VR. In contrast, some AR HMDs like the HoloLens 2 already include cameras for hand tracking. To visualize eye movement, eye tracking has to be part of the HMD or needs to be additionally added [62]. legs and feet position and rotation can only be created by additional tracking, for instance using VR trackers [94], a Kinect Sensor [50] or optical tracking [25]. Also facial tracking requires added equipment like a Kinect [50, 61] or an external camera [26]. Wu et al. [91] show that an avatar based on four depth sensors can create a higher virtual body ownership and better non-verbal communication performance in comparison to a inverse kinematic avatar controlled by controllers.

3.6 Application Domains

We noticed that the representation style is related to the used application area (see Fig. 2). Realistic avatars seem to be used as the most versatile representations applied to every domain, but overall in medical use cases (4 of 5) due to the importance of realistic proportions and trust towards the avatar. Realistic, on the other hand are predominantly used in domains for training and engineering (5 of 7). Stylized avatars are used in use cases that have a playful character (2 of 2). Yoon et al. [94], for instance, emphasize that a realistic avatar should be preferred for work collaboration and have potential to create a higher body ownership [43]. Whereas point cloud avatars can be most pleasant in virtual coach setting [57]. Yet,

for educational purposes, we found that non-realistic avatars are used equally (2 times, realistic avatars: 2 times).

3.7 Gender and Ethnicity

During the coding process, we noticed an imbalance towards ethnicity and gender in avatar research (see Fig. 4). We found that most avatar representations used in the studies were *only male* (21 of 49) compared to *only female* (4 of 49). Only 19 of 49 studies used avatars with both genders or neutral avatars (6 of 49). Still, no paper has explicitly examined non-binary avatars. Additionally, more male participants (57.7%, female: 42.3%) were included in the evaluations. Although Yassien et al. [93] found that matching gender teams are perceived as more productive and supportive. This is in contrast to the fact that although almost half of the participants were female, the majority of the avatars were *only male* (42%). Besides gender, we found that the majority of avatars used in the studies displayed only white ethnics (34 of 49), while in 1 paper the avatars were seemingly asian.

4 DISCUSSION

Our systematic review aims to survey and synthesize the literature that focus on avatar-supported collaboration in immersive environments. The goal is to provide a critical appraisal of not only the impact of different aspects of an avatar, which can guide researchers for future evaluations on avatar-supported immersive collaboration.

Representation style matters when building avatars for specific application domains. The majority of papers used realistic avatars (33 of 49). Although they can achieve higher presence, realistic avatars may not always be the best choice to represent a user [30]. For instance, when learners in an educational or training scenario are visualized, application domains tend to favor stylized avatars or mannequins to support a playful character or focus on features, such as gaze visualization, as limiting the representation style the users can focus on the task itself and lower perceived social presence. However, in these scenarios, the teaching actor should be visualized as realistic as possible, as it can lead to higher trust. Overall, we assume that avatar appropriateness is strongly task-dependent and needs to be considered for each use case independently.

Avatar richness differs between the immersive environments. We found that different modalities to represent a users body a used more often in specific immersive environments. Fig. 2 shows, that various movement visualizations are present. The richness of visualization is mostly limited by tracking and sensors, from a realization stand point many variants are possible. This difference is mainly due to the different hardware that exists for AR and VR. For instance, inverse kinematic for avatars in VR is much easier to realize due to VR controllers compared to AR, where the hands of a user usually need to be in the field of view of the HMD to properly work. Research suggests that full-body avatars should be favored compared to other body representation forms, as here, the highest body ownership for the user embodying the avatar can be achieved as well as the highest feeling of presence for other users being present in the same immersive environment. Although displaying a full body may not be possible in every situation with current HMDs, due to hardware or software restrictions (e.g. limited render capabilities), a good compromise needs to be found, which again is task-dependent.

Gender and ethnic bias limits avatar variation. Our results showed that 23 out of 49 publications used avatars that were only female (4 of 49) or had an option for both genders (19 of 49), compared to a total of 39 for male avatars. This does not reflect the general population well and needs to be addressed in future research. Additionally, avatars with multiple ethnic backgrounds need to be included. We assume most researcher use *white* avatars to cover most participants, yet again, this does not reflect the general population.

Tracking modalities can limit the avatar representation. While analyzing the literature, we found that tracking modalities seem to limit the avatar representations, with regard to their style and body parts that are represented. Although some researchers already address this issue by implementing alternative approaches to visualize avatars while using less hardware and instead using software-side approaches to compensate for missing VR trackers or other components. This is a good direction and should be followed in future research.

Communication is key. Non-verbal communication channels, besides body movement itself, is used less often (eye gaze: 8 of 49, facial expression: 5 of 49) compared to voice (29 of 49). Yet, minimal behavioral cues can influence the sensing of co-presence and benefit social communication between collaboration partners. Although missing social cues can partially be compensated, it is important to implement even small cues, as this can already increase a users awareness, as avatar-supported multi-user environments have the potential to increase social interaction [27, 71]. We advocate implementing more facial expressions, as this, according to the reviewed literature, increases social behaviors and helps users experience emotional states. This may be particularly important when investigating social group dynamics in immersive environments. If no hardware solution exists or isn't available, emotional states and facial expressions can be estimated through the tone of voice or passively activated through the use in an augmented form of emojis.

Avatar fidelity changes with the immersive environment and collaboration type. Researchers used different a avatar fidelity, with regard to representation style, depending on the collaboration type. As mentioned earlier, avatar-supported systems are used more often when collaboration is not taking place in the same place and where they might have the highest potential to enrich the communication between collaborators. Yet, realistic avatars are prevalent in co-located collaboration compared to other collaboration types. Here, collaboration partner may not know each other and, thus, a realistic representation might not be necessary as no mismatch between representation and collaboration partner can occur. However, as this is an assumption on our end and not fully backed up by the literature, it needs further investigation.

5 LIMITATIONS

The field of avatars is already broadly researched. To narrow down the literature surveyed in this paper, we only included publications from six top venues according to CORE [66]. Although this may increase the quality of the literature from a meta view, we may missed quality literature from other venues. For the scope of this paper, we only included literature that target avatar-supported immersive collaboration. Additionally, we only included publications containing an image of an avatar. This rule was applied to ensure that we get a clear visual understanding of the avatars used. Some literature might be missed in this survey because of a missing picture.

6 INTERACTIVE SURVEY BROWSER

To support the analysis and provide a lightweight interfaces for readers of this paper, we built a web-based tool to interactively filter by different properties (see Fig. 5, Link: <https://visvar.github.io/vr-ar-avatar-survey/>). This includes authors, venues, keywords, research topics and other filters. Different search parameters can be combined to enable a broader search, for example with settings that we have not further pursued in this paper. In addition to filtering the papers, the website offers various interactive visualizations to give a deeper insight into the collected data. Some visualizations are also part of this paper (see figures). In addition to bar charts, line charts can be displayed there as small multiples of keywords and research topics, a visualization of modality correlations shows frequencies in combination with teaser images and various other supporting displays.

Figure 5: Our interactive browser (<https://visvar.github.io/vr-ar-avatars-survey/>). Results can be refined by keywords, authors, conference, type of publication, collaboration and representation type, as well as other reasonable filters. Results by different visualizations. On the right side the publications that match the search criteria are listed.

7 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we analyzed 49 papers from six different venues focusing on avatar-supported collaboration in immersive environments. We were able to identify avatar representations that are predominant in literature for various reasons, for instance due to their usage context or due to hardware limitations. Our most surprising finding is the imbalance of avatars with regard to gender diversity and ethnicity. Here, we hope in future studies, this imbalance is addressed by researchers.

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